

MODELING OF AEOLIAN VIBRATION OF OVERHEAD HIGH-VOLTAGE TRANSMISSION LINES USING THE FINITE ELEMENT METHOD

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ABSTRACT: In this paper, a commercial finite element program - ADINA (Automatic Dynamic Incremental Nonlinear Analysis) [1] is used to model Aeolian vibration. The compressible fluid flow is described using the Navier-Stokes equations. For the fluid (air), the flow assumptions include: flow dimension of 2D (in YZ Plane), low speed compressible flow type. For the cylinder (conductor), the model is 2D and isotropic elastic material, plus a stiff spring in the Y-direction and a weaker spring in the Z-direction. Simulations using ADINA are not completed at this stage.

KEYWORDS: Aeolian vibration, overhead high-voltage transmission lines, fluids-structure interaction, span lengths, sub-span lengths.

INTRODUCTION

Of all the forces that cause static and dynamic action on flexible structures, such as transmission line cables, wind plays a significant role along with rain and earthquake. The effect of wind on the cables should be considered first, since it results in large deflection. A structure immersed in a given flow field is subjected to aerodynamics forces, which include drag (i.e. along- wind forces), act in the direction of the mean flow and lift (i.e. across wind forces), act perpendicular to the direction of the wind flow. For different wind velocities, these drag and lift forces vary and hence result in different types of conductor motions.

Observations in early 1920's showed that the breaks of transmission line cables were attributed to metal fatigue, resulting from the fact that the lines, under certain wind conditions were vibrating. Those observations also indicated that the vibrations occurred within a range of velocities of wind (i.e.1 to 7m/s) and recognized the fact that air turbulences decreased the severity of vibrations. These types of high frequency-low amplitude vibration, resulting due to wind of low velocities, are called Aeolian vibrations.

In this report, the finite element program-ADINA (Automatic Dynamic Incremental Nonlinear Analysis) [1] is used to model Aeolian vibration.

Vortex Shedding Around a Cylinder

Aeolian excitation is the result of vortex shedding in the wake of the conductor. These vortices form a stable vortex street in the sub critical range of Reynolds number ($300 \leq Re \leq 150000$) [2-7].

Within this range of Re the excitation is assumed to be independent of Re. Reynolds number is defined by the following equation:

$$\text{Re} = \frac{VD}{\nu} \quad (1)$$

where V: wind velocity normal to the cable

ν : dynamic viscosity of the fluid

D: characteristics dimension of the body (diameter of conductor)

For $R^{-1} \neq 0$, governing equations may be cast using Navier-Stokes equations.

Strouhal first reported the pronounced regularity of wake effects, and pointed out that the vortex shedding phenomena can be described in terms of a non-dimensional number, known as STROUHAL number. It is defined as

$$S = \frac{f_s D}{V} \quad (2)$$

where,

f_s : frequency of the full cycles of vortex shedding

D: is the characteristics dimension of the body projected on a plane normal to mean flow velocity

V: velocity of incoming flow (which is assumed turbulent).

When a body is subjected to wind flow, the separation of flow occurs around the body. This produces force on the body, a pressure force on the windward side and a suction force on the leeward side. The pressure and suction forces result in the formation of vortices in the wake region causing structural deflections on the body. The shedding of vorticity balances the change of fluid momentum along the entire body surface. So vortex shedding is the instance where alternating low pressure zones are generated on the downwind side. These alternating low pressure zones cause the conductor to move towards the low pressure zone, causing movement perpendicular to the direction of the wind. When the critical wind speed of the conductor is reached, these forces can cause the conductor to resonate where large forces and deflections are experienced.

The transverse flow around a cylinder has been the subject of continued experimental and theoretical studies [7]. Most of the experimental studies are based on flow visualization and they reveal that as the Reynolds number (based on free stream velocity and cylinder diameter) increases, the flow displays a series of different structures. So simulation of vortex shedding is important in the design of equipment that may be subject to flow induced vibration, such as overhead transmission lines.

Figure 1 Aeolian vibration

Fatigue failure is the most common damage resulting from Aeolian vibrations. Moreover it may cause fatigue to other line components such as armor rod, dampers, ties, insulators and tower members etc.

Wind Power Input

As a vibrating conductor receives energy from the wind, its amplitude rises to a point at which its internal dissipation balances the energy input from the wind. The mechanical power transferred from the wind to a vibrating conductor has been determined by Bate and Callow [3] and can be expressed in the general form as:

$$P = d^4 f^3 fnc\left(\frac{Y}{d}\right) \quad (3)$$

where

P: mechanical power in Watts per unit length of the conductor

d: conductor diameter

f: frequency of vibration

$fnc\left(\frac{Y}{d}\right)$: a function of the vibration amplitude, expressed in terms of the conductor diameter

Bahtovska [4] later determined that the power of aerodynamic forces can be expressed as:

$$P_w = lf^3 D^4 \frac{1}{\pi} \sum_{i=1}^{10} b_i \left(\frac{A}{D}\right)^i \quad (4)$$

Wind induced vibrations of small amplitude are described by:

$$EIw'''' - Tw'' + \rho\dot{w} = q(x, t) + \bar{d}(w, \dot{w}, t) \quad (5)$$

where

EI is the bending stiffness of the cable

T is the tension

ρ is the mass per unit length

$w(x,t)$ is the transverse displacement of the cable

$q(x,t)$ is the wind force due to vortex shedding

\bar{d} is the material damping

Fluid Structure Interaction (FSI)

Long flexible cables are commonly used for electrical power transmission lines and numerous studies of their interaction with a fluid flow and the resulting oscillatory instabilities have taken place. When exposed to wind, as any aerodynamically bluff body, cables are characterised by a flow separation from their surface and a wake carrying shed vortices downstream (vortex shedding).

The methodology to be used in the modeling of flow involves solving the structure and fluid equations simultaneously incorporating the fluid structure interaction. Fluid structure interaction is a phenomenon where a fluid flowing around a structure causes it to change shape due to flow-induced and shear loads or to move and spin. The deformation of a solid structure, in turn, changes the boundary condition of the fluid problem. FSI is often a transient occurrence, where the structural motions are dynamic and continuously vary with time. So the simulations that result involve coupling of fluid and solid mechanics. FSI modeling needs the simultaneous solving of both the equations of structure and fluid.

Model Layout

A model, adopted from [7] is used in our investigation. The circular rigid cylinder under consideration (Figure 1) is elastically mounted with its longitudinal axis transversally to the direction of the flowing fluid (cylinder mass m , length L , diameter D , spring constant k , fluid velocity V). A small amount of viscous damping force may be admitted (damping constant d) in parallel with the spring. A very stiff spring may also be included along the direction of the wind velocity.

Figure 1: Solid model [7]

Figure 2: Model of a vortex-induced vibration of a cylinder

A finite element model is implemented in ADINA as shown in Figures 3 and 4.

Figure 4 Cylinder (conductor) with springs

Figure 5 Fluid model

For the fluid, the flow assumptions include: flow dimension of 2D (in YZ Plane), low speed compressible flow type. For the cylinder (conductor), the model is 2D and isotropic elastic material, plus a stiff spring in the Y-direction and a weaker spring in the Z-direction.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

A finite element model for Aeolian vibration of high voltage transmission lines has been laid out. Simulations using ADINA are not completed at this stage.

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